

Supporting Information for

How we can improve ARGET ATRP in an aqueous
system: Honey as an unusual solution for
polymerization of (meth)acrylates

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S1. Experimental Section

Materials. Various types of honeys (multiflorous honey, sunflower honey, rapeseed honey nectar, linden honey, and honeydew honey) were procured from local markets in Rzeszow (Poland). 3,5-Dinitrosalicylic acid ($\geq 98.0\%$), potassium sodium tartrate tetrahydrate ($\geq 99.0\%$), sodium hydroxide (NaOH, $\geq 98\%$), ethyl 2-bromoisobutyrate (EBiB, 98%), 2-bromopropionitril (BPN, 97%), sodium bromide (NaBr, $>99\%$), α -D-glucose (96%), sodium dodecyl sulfate (SDS, $\geq 99.0\%$), hexadecane (HD, 99.0%) and copper(II) bromide ($\text{Cu}^{\text{II}}\text{Br}_2$, 99.9%) were purchased from Sigma Aldrich. Dimethylsulfoxide- d_6 (DMSO, 99.8%, 0.03% v/v TMS) and chloroform- d (CDCl_3 , 99.8%, 0.03% TMS, stabilized by 0.5% w/w Ag foil) was purchased from Deutero GmbH. *n*-Hexane ($\geq 97.0\%$) and ethanol ($\geq 97.0\%$) were purchased from Honeywell Research Chemicals, while ethyl 2-bromophenylacetate (EBPA, 97%) was purchased Acros Organics. Proceeding substances were used without further purification. 2-Hydroxyethyl 2-bromoisobutyrate (OH-EBiB) was prepared according to previously described procedure [1]. ATRP initiators for the preparation of branched architectures were prepared according to the procedure described in the papers, namely, synthesis of Trox-Br₁₀ was described in [2], while Rib-Br₂ in [3], Tris(2-pyridylmethyl) amine (TPMA) was prepared in compliance with the published procedure [4], $\text{Cu}^{\text{II}}\text{Br}_2$ /TPMA catalyst complex was obtained as reported [5]. 2-(Dimethylamino)ethyl methacrylate (DMAEMA, $>99\%$), glycidyl methacrylate (GMA, $>99\%$), 2-hydroxyethyl methacrylate (HEMA, 97%), di(ethylene glycol) methyl ether methacrylate (DEGMA, 95%), 2-hydroxyethyl acrylate (HEA, 96%) and *n*-butyl acrylate (*n*BA, 99%) were purchased from Sigma Aldrich and passed through a column filled with basic aluminum oxide to remove the inhibitor, and *N*-isopropylacrylamide (99%, Sigma Aldrich) was recrystallized from hexane.

Analysis. In order to determine the kinetics of the polymerizations and the structure of the final polymer products the proton nuclear magnetic resonance (^1H NMR) spectra were carried in deuterated solvent – DMSO- d_6 and chloroform- d using Bruker Avance 500 MHz spectrometer (25

°C). Molecular weights (MWs) and molecular weight distributions (MWDs, M_w/M_n , D) were determined by gel permeation chromatography (GPC) using a Shimadzu (Kyoto, Japan) modular system equipped with a CBM-40 system controller, SIL-20AHT automatic injector, the RID-20A differential refractive-index detector and PSS GRAM combination columns made of stainless steel (V4A); For determination of MWs and MWDs of PDMAEMA, PGMA, and PHEMA the columns set was composed of one precolumn, one 100 Å column and two 3,000 Å columns, the temperature of the columns was maintained at 35 °C using a CTO-20A oven, the eluent was *N,N*-dimethylformamide (HPLC grade, with 0.01 M LiCl) and the flow rate was kept at 1 mL/min using a LC-40 pump. While, for determination of MWs and MWDs of PnBA the columns set was composed of precolumn, and three Repro-Gel 5 µm columns (500 Å, 10,000 Å and 100,000 Å), the temperature of the columns was maintained at 35°C using a CTO-20A oven, the eluent was tetrahydrofuran (HPLC grade) and the flow rate was kept at 1 mL/min using a LC-40 pump. A molecular weight calibration curve was produced using commercial narrow molecular weight distribution polystyrene standards (PSS Polymer Standards Service, Mainz, Germany). The UV-Vis spectra were obtained on a Hewlett-Packard (Waldbronn, Germany) Model HP-8453 diode array rapid scan spectrophotometer using a quartz cell with an optical length of 1 cm.

DNS assay for determination of reducing sugar content in various kinds of honey. 3, 5-Dinitrosalicylic acid reagent was prepared as described in previous reported procedure [6], namely, 1.6 g NaOH was added to 75 mL of distilled water under continuous stirring, followed by the addition of 1g of 3,5-dinitrosalicylic acid. Finally, 3 g of sodium potassium tartrate was added and the remaining volume was filled with distilled water to make 100 mL of DNS reagent. A series of calibration standard curves of glucose were prepared by DNS assay at a concentration range of 0.4–1 mg/mL. DNS assay was carried out by placing the 1 mL of standard or test sample in a 20 mL test tube and then 3 mL of DNS reagent was added. The reaction mixture was heated in boiling water for 5 min. The absorbance spectra of the test samples were measured at 540 nm using 10 mm path length

quartz cuvettes in the UV-Vis spectrophotometer. Blank test was performed in 1 mL of distilled water instead of the test sample. For determination of the concentration of reducing sugars in honey samples, 6 mg/mL solutions of various kinds of honey were prepared, followed by placing the 1 mL of the sample in a 20 mL test tube and then 3 mL of DNS reagent was added. The measurements were conducted analogously to calibration curve samples.

General procedure for the synthesis of PDMAEMA in distilled water by internally-controlled ARGET ATRP in the presence of air. A series of aqueous ARGET ATRP reactions were carried out with different ATRP initiators. NaBr (0.1029 g, 1.0 mmol), 5 mL of distilled water, DMAEMA (5 mL, 29.6 mmol) and 0.053 mL Cu^{II}Br₂/TPMA stock solution (0.05 M in DMF) were introduced into Schlenk flask containing magnetic stirring bar. Then ATRP initiator: 29.0 μL of EBiB (0.2 mmol) or 28.6 μL of OH-EBiB (0.2 mmol) or 34.5 μL of EBPA (0.2 mmol) or 26.5 μL of BPN (0.2 mmol) was injected, and the initial sample was taken. The flask was sealed with a cap. The reaction was carried out at room temperature (22 °C) in the presence of air. Samples were taken at short time intervals and analyzed by GPC and ¹H NMR.

General procedure for the synthesis of PDMAEMA in the presence of air by ARGET ATRP accelerated by reducing sugars. A series of aqueous ARGET ATRP reactions were carried out varying reducing sugar content, NaBr concentration, and honey type. NaBr (0.1029 g, 1.0 mmol or 0.2058 g, 2.0 mmol, or 0.3087 g, 3.0 mmol, or 0.4116 g, 0.4 mmol), 5 mL of various honey solutions (2.5–10% w/v in reaction mixture, containing 0.8 mmol–3.1 mmol of reducing sugars) or 5 mL of glucose (140.0 mg, 0.8 mmol) solution, DMAEMA (5 mL, 29.6 mmol) and 0.053 mL Cu^{II}Br₂/TPMA stock solution (0.05 M in DMF) were introduced into Schlenk flask containing magnetic stirring bar. Then 34.5 μL of EBPA (0.2 mmol) was injected, and the initial sample was taken. The flask was sealed with a cap. The reaction was carried out at room temperature (22 °C) in the presence of air. Samples were taken at short time intervals and analyzed by GPC and ¹H NMR. One of the final

polymer product were purified by precipitation in n-hexane, dried under vacuum for 24 h, and characterized by ^1H NMR (**Figure S15**).

General procedure for the synthesis of PGMA by ARGET ATRP controlled by reducing sugars present in honey. NaBr (0.1029 g, 1.0 mmol), 5 mL or 6 mL of honey solutions (2.5% w/v in reaction mixture in 80/20 v/v ethanol/distilled water, containing 0.8 mmol of reducing sugars), GMA (5 mL, 37.0 mmol or 4 mL, 29.6 mmol) and 0.074 or 0.059 mL $\text{Cu}^{\text{II}}\text{Br}_2/\text{TPMA}$ stock solution (0.05 M in DMF) were introduced into Schlenk flask containing magnetic stirring bar. Then 43.1 μL or 34.5 μL of EBPA (0.25 or 0.20 mmol) was injected, and the initial sample was taken. The flask was sealed with a cap and bubbled with Ar for 15 min. The reaction was carried out at room temperature (22 °C). Samples were taken at short time intervals and analyzed by GPC and ^1H NMR. One of the final polymer product were purified by precipitation in water, dried under vacuum for 24 h, and characterized by ^1H NMR (**Figure S16**).

General procedure for the synthesis of POEGMA, PDEGMA, PHEA and PNIPAM by ARGET ATRP controlled by reducing sugars present in honey. NaBr (0.1029 g, 1.0 mmol or 0.4116 g, 1.0 mmol), 5 mL or 9 mL of honey solutions (2.5–10% w/v in reaction mixture, containing 0.8 mmol–3.1 mmol of reducing sugars), OEGMA (5 mL, 10.7 mmol) or DEGMA (4.7 mL, 25.5 mmol) or HEA (4.6 mL, 39.8 mmol) or NIPAM (0.9088 g, 0.8 mmol) and 0.019–0.398 mL $\text{Cu}^{\text{II}}\text{Br}_2/\text{TPMA}$ stock solution (0.05 M in DMF) were introduced into Schlenk flask containing magnetic stirring bar. Then 12.5 μL of EBPA (0.07 mmol) for polymerization of OEGMA, 29.8 μL of EBPA (0.17 mmol) for polymerization of DEGMA, 38.9 μL of EBiB (0.27 mmol) for polymerization of HEA, and 7.8 μL of OH-EBiB (0.05 mmol) for polymerization of NIPAM was injected, and the initial sample was taken. The flask was sealed with a cap and bubbled with Ar for 15 min. The reaction was carried out at room temperature (22 °C). Samples were taken at short time intervals and analyzed by GPC and ^1H NMR.

General procedure for the synthesis of *n*BA by a miniemulsion ARGET ATRP controlled by reducing sugars present in honey. *n*BA (1.68 mL, 18 vol% in water), EBiB (1.4 μ L, 0.01 mmol or 14.3 μ L, 0.1 mmol), and HD (0.21 mL, 0.71 mmol) were mixed to form the oil phase. Cu^{II}Br₂/TPMA stock solution (160 μ L of 0.05 M in distilled water), NaBr (0.0870 g, 0.85 mmol), and SDS (0.0870 g, 0.32 mmol, 6.2% w/w to monomer) were dissolved in 7.93 mL of honey solution (0.05-10% w/v in reaction mixture, containing 0.02-558.31 mmol of reducing sugars). The oil and aqueous solutions were mixed (total volume \approx 10.0 mL), placed in an ice bath, and homogenized by an ultrasonic probe sonicator, amplitude = 25% for 10 min (application and rest time of 1 s each, 20 min in total). The flask was immersed in a 65 °C oil bath. Nitrogen was bubbled into the miniemulsion for 15 min starting the synthesis. Samples were withdrawn periodically to follow the monomer conversion by gravimetric analysis, while M_n and M_w/M_n were determined by GPC. The final product was recovered by drying the miniemulsion on an aluminum weighing dish, dissolved in THF, passed through a neutral alumina column, and dried in a vacuum for 2 days, and characterized by ¹H NMR (**Figure S17**).

General procedure for chain extension of *n*BA from P*n*BA by a miniemulsion ARGET ATRP controlled by reducing sugars present in honey. The P*n*BA-Br macroinitiator was prepared via the reducing sugars-controlled miniemulsion SI-ARGET ATRP method as described above with 0.3% w/v honey and targeted DP equal to 120 (**Table 5**, entry 3). For the chain extension experiment, polymerization was carried out *via* miniemulsion SI-ARGET ATRP controlled by reducing sugars present in honey under the following reaction conditions: *n*BA (1.66 mL, 18 vol% in water), P*n*BA-Br (0.1228 g, 0.01 mmol), and HD (0.21 mL, 0.71 mmol) were mixed to form the oil phase. Cu^{II}Br₂/TPMA stock solution (160 μ L of 0.05 M in distilled water), NaBr (0.0870 g, 0.85 mmol), and SDS (0.0870 g, 0.32 mmol, 6.2% w/w to monomer) were dissolved in 7.84 mL of honey solution (0.3% w/v in reaction mixture, containing 0.08 mmol of reducing sugars). The oil and aqueous solutions were mixed (total volume \approx 10.0 mL), placed in an ice bath, and homogenized by an

ultrasonic probe sonicator, amplitude = 25% for 10 min (application and rest time of 1 s each, 20 min in total). The flask was immersed in a 65 °C oil bath. Nitrogen was bubbled into the miniemulsion for 15 min starting the synthesis. Samples were withdrawn periodically to follow the monomer conversion by gravimetric analysis, while M_n and M_w/M_n were determined by GPC.

General procedure for the polymerization of *n*BA from Trox-Br₁₀ by a miniemulsion ARGET ATRP controlled by reducing sugars present in honey. *n*BA (1.68 mL, 18 vol% in water), Trox-Br₁₀ (0.0043-0.0217 g, 1.9-9.7 μmol), and HD (0.21 mL, 0.71 mmol) were mixed to form the oil phase. Cu^{II}Br₂/TPMA stock solution (160 μL of 0.05 M in distilled water), NaBr (0.0870 g, 0.85 mmol), and SDS (0.0870 g, 0.32 mmol, 6.2% w/w to monomer) were dissolved in 7.93 mL of honey solution (0.3-10% w/v in reaction mixture, containing 0.08-558.31 mmol of reducing sugars). The oil and aqueous solutions were mixed (total volume ≈ 10.0 mL), placed in an ice bath, and homogenized by an ultrasonic probe, amplitude = 25% for 10 min (application and rest time of 1 s each, 20 min in total). The flask was immersed in a 65 °C oil bath. Nitrogen was bubbled into the miniemulsion for 15 min starting the synthesis. Samples were withdrawn periodically to follow the monomer conversion by gravimetric analysis, while M_n and M_w/M_n were determined by GPC. The final product was recovered by drying the miniemulsion on an aluminum weighing dish, dissolved in THF, passed through a neutral alumina column, and dried in a vacuum for 2 days, and characterized by ¹H NMR (Figure S18).

General procedure for chain extension of *n*BA from Trox-(P*n*BA-Br)₁₀ by a miniemulsion ARGET ATRP controlled by reducing sugars present in honey. The Trox-(P*n*BA-Br)₁₀ macroinitiator was prepared via the reducing sugars-controlled miniemulsion SI-ARGET ATRP method as described above with 10% w/v honey and targeted DP equal to 120 (Table 6, entry 2). For the chain extension experiment following reaction conditions were used: *n*BA (1.68 mL, 18 vol% in water), Trox-(P*n*BA-Br)₁₀ (0.0947 g, 1.0 μmol), and HD (0.21 mL, 0.71 mmol) were mixed to form the oil phase. Cu^{II}Br₂/TPMA stock solution (160 μL of 0.05 M in distilled water), NaBr (0.0870 g,

0.85 mmol), and SDS (0.0870 g, 0.32 mmol, 6.2% w/w to monomer) were dissolved in 7.84 mL of honey solution (10% w/v in reaction mixture, containing 0.56 mmol of reducing sugars). The oil and aqueous solutions were mixed (total volume \approx 10.0 mL), placed in an ice bath, and homogenized by an ultrasonic probe, amplitude = 25% for 10 min (application and rest time of 1 s each, 20 min in total). The flask was immersed in a 65 °C oil bath. Nitrogen was bubbled into the miniemulsion for 15 min starting the synthesis. Samples were withdrawn periodically to follow the monomer conversion by gravimetric analysis, while M_n and M_w/M_n were determined by GPC.

General procedure for the polymerization of *n*BA from Rib-Br₂ by a miniemulsion ARGET ATRP controlled by reducing sugars present in honey. *n*BA (1.68 mL, 18 vol% in water), Rib-Br₂ (0.0066-0.0328 g, 9.7-48.7 μ mol), and HD (0.21 mL, 0.71 mmol) were mixed to form the oil phase. The synthesis was also conducted without HD. Cu^{II}Br₂/TPMA stock solution (160 μ L of 0.05 M in distilled water), NaBr (0.0870 g, 0.85 mmol), and SDS (0.0870 g, 0.32 mmol, 6.2% w/w to monomer) were dissolved in 7.93 mL of honey solution (0.3-10% w/v in reaction mixture, containing 0.08-558.31 mmol of reducing sugars). The oil and aqueous solutions were mixed (total volume \approx 10.0 mL), placed in an ice bath, and homogenized by an ultrasonic probe, amplitude = 25% for 10 min (application and rest time of 1 s each, 20 min in total). The flask was immersed in a 65 °C oil bath. Nitrogen was bubbled into the miniemulsion for 15 min starting the synthesis. Samples were withdrawn periodically to follow the monomer conversion by gravimetric analysis, while M_n and M_w/M_n were determined by GPC. The final product was recovered by drying the miniemulsion on an aluminum weighing dish, dissolved in THF, passed through a neutral alumina column, and dried in a vacuum for 2 days, and characterized by ¹H NMR (**Figure S19**).

S2. Polymerization of DMAEMA by internally-controlled ARGET ATRP in distilled water

Table S1. Selection of the ATRP initiator for polymerization of DMAEMA in deionized water by internally controlled ARGET ATRP.^a

Entry	Initiator	t [h]	Conv ^b [%]	k_p^{appb}	$M_{n,theo}^c$ [x10 ⁻³]	$M_{n,app}^d$ [x10 ⁻³]	M_w/M_n^d	I_{eff}^f [%]
1	EBiB	2	46	0.296	11,1	36,4	1.61	31
2	OH-EBiB	2	58	0.393	13,9	35,7	1.60	39
3	EBPA	2	27 40 ^f	0.161 0.166 ^f	6,5 9,7 ^f	10,6 20,8 ^f	1.72 1.72 ^f	62 46 ^f
4	BPN	2	57	0.448	13,3	31,1	1.73	44

^aGeneral reaction conditions: $[DMAEMA]_0/[Initiator]_0/[Cu^{II}Br_2/TPMA]_0 = 150/1/0.014$; $V_{tot} = 10$ mL; $[DMAEMA]_0 = 3.0$ M; $[Cu^{II}Br_2/TPMA]_0 = 90$ ppm; T = room temperature (22 °C); Air atmosphere; $[NaBr]_0 = 0.1$ M; Distilled water as a reaction medium; ^bMonomer conversion and apparent rate constant of propagation (k_p^{app}) were determined by NMR [7]; ^c $M_{n,theo} = ([DMAEMA]_0/[Initiator]_0) \cdot conversion \cdot M_{DMAEMA} + M_{Initiator}$; ^dapparent M_n and M_w/M_n were determined by GPC; ^eInitiation efficiency, $I_{eff} = (M_{n,theo}/M_{n,app}) \cdot 100\%$; ^fThe results for polymerization conducted for 3 hours.

Figure S1. Selection of the ATRP initiator for polymerization of DMAEMA in deionized water by internally controlled ARGET ATRP. (a) First-order kinetics plot of monomer conversion vs. polymerization time, and (b) M_n and M_w/M_n vs. monomer conversion. GPC traces of the polymers

prepared in the reaction system containing (c) EBiB, (d) OH-EBiB, (e) EBPA, and (f) BPN.

Reactions conditions as in **Table S1**.

S3. Determination of concentration of reducing sugars in honey by DNS assay

3,5-dinitrosalicylic acid (DNS) assay has been widely employed for the estimation of reducing sugars in samples. This assay tests for the presence of free carbonyl group (C=O), the so-called reducing sugars. The basic principle of DNS assay includes the reduction of one of the nitro groups in 3,5-dinitrosalicylic acid to 3-amino-5-nitrosalicylic acid under alkaline conditions and subsequent oxidation of the aldehyde groups in substrates to carboxylic acids [6].

Figure S2. Absorbance against concentration plot for glucose in DNS assay. All the absorbance values were recorded at 540 nm at room temperature.

Table S2. The content of reducing sugars in various kinds of honey determined by DNS assay.

Type of honey	C _{solution} [mg/mL]	C _{honey} [%]
Linden	0.139	66.0
Honeydew	0.141	66.8
Rapeseed honey nectar	0.138	65.5
Sunflower	0.129	72.2
Multiflorus	0.114	55.4

S4. Polymerization of DMAEMA by internally-controlled ARGET ATRP accelerated by reducing sugars present in honey

Figure S3. GPC traces of the polymers prepared in the reaction system containing (a) 10% w/v honey and 0.1 M NaBr, (b) 10% w/v honey and 0.2 M NaBr, (c) 10% w/v honey and 0.3 M NaBr, (d) 7.5% w/v honey and 0.1 M NaBr, (e) 5.0% w/v honey and 0.1 M NaBr, (f) 2.5% w/v honey and 0.1 M NaBr, (g) 2.5% w/v honey and 0.2 M NaBr, (h) 2.5% w/v honey and 0.3 M NaBr, and (i) 2.5% w/v honey and 0.4 M NaBr. Reaction conditions as in **Table 1**.

Figure S4. GPC traces of the polymers prepared in the reaction system containing various kinds of honey: (a) sunflower honey, (b) rapeseed honey nectar, (c) linden honey, and (d) honeydew honey. Reactions conditions as in **Table 3**.

S5. Polymerization of (meth)acrylates and *N*-isopropylacrylamide through ARGET ATRP controlled by reducing sugars present in honey

Figure S5. Polymerization of GMA by ARGET ATRP controlled by reducing sugars present in various honey. (a) Semilogarithmic kinetic plots, and (b) evolutions of M_n and M_w/M_n vs monomer conversion. GPC traces of polymers prepared in (c) 50% v/v and (d) 40% v/v GMA solution. Reactions conditions as in **Table 4**.

Table S3. Polymerization of (meth)acrylates in honey solution by ARGET ATRP.^a

Entry	Monomer	[RS] ₀ [% w/v]	t [h]	Conv ^b [%]	k_p^{appb}	$M_{n,theo}^c$ [x10 ⁻³]	$M_{n,app}^d$ [x10 ⁻³]	M_w/M_n^d	I^{effe} [%]
1	HEMA	10	44.83	7	0.002	1,6		<i>f</i>	
2	DEGMA	10	21.2			<i>g</i>			
3	HEA	10	43.83			<i>g</i>			
4	NIPAM	10	48.45			<i>g</i>			

^aGeneral reaction conditions: [Monomer]₀/[Initiator]₀/[Cu^{II}Br₂/TPMA]₀/[RS]₀ = 150/1/0.075/12 for entry 1 and 3, [Monomer]₀/[Initiator]₀/[Cu^{II}Br₂/TPMA]₀/[RS]₀ = 150/1/0.075/18 for entry 2 and [Monomer]₀/[Initiator]₀/[Cu^{II}Br₂/TPMA]₀/[RS]₀ = 150/1/0.075/58 for entry 4; V_{tot} = 10 mL; EBPA as ATRP initiator for entry 1 and 2, EBiB as ATRP initiator for entry 3 and EBIB-OH as ATRP

initiator for entry 4; [HEMA]₀ = 3.8 M, [DEGMA]₀ = 2.6 M, [HEA]₀ = 4.0 M, [NIPAM]₀ = 0.8 M; [Cu^{II}Br₂/TPMA]₀ = 500 ppm; [NaBr]₀ = 0.1 M; T = room temperature (22 °C); Inert gas (Ar) atmosphere; Honey solutions in distilled water solution as a reaction medium; ^bMonomer conversion and apparent rate constant of propagation (k_p^{app}) were determined by NMR [7]; ^c $M_{n,\text{theo}} = ([\text{Monomer}]_0/[\text{Initiator}]_0) \cdot \text{conversion} \cdot M_{\text{Monomer}} + M_{\text{Initiator}}$; ^dapparent M_n and M_w/M_n were determined by GPC; ^eInitiation efficiency, $I_{\text{eff}} = (M_{n,\text{theo}}/M_{n,\text{app}}) \cdot 100\%$; ^fNot determined. ^gReaction did not proceed.

S6. Polymerization of *n*BA through ARGET ATRP in miniemulsion controlled by reducing sugars present in honey

Figure S6. GPC traces of P*n*BA prepared by ARGET ATRP in miniemulsion controlled by reducing sugars present honey using various conditions as follows: (a) $DP_{\text{target}} = 1200$, $[Cu^{II}Br_2]_0/[RS]_0 = 1/379$ (**Table 5**, entry 1), (b) $DP_{\text{target}} = 120$, $[Cu^{II}Br_2]_0/[RS]_0 = 1/379$ (**Table 5**, entry 2), (c) $DP_{\text{target}} = 120$, $[Cu^{II}Br_2]_0/[RS]_0 = 1/10$ (**Table 5**, entry 3), (d) $DP_{\text{target}} = 120$, $[Cu^{II}Br_2]_0/[RS]_0 = 1/2$ (**Table 5**, entry 4), and (e) chain extension experiment, $DP_{\text{target}} = 1200$, $[Cu^{II}Br_2]_0/[RS]_0 = 1/10$ (**Table 5**, entry 5).

S7. Synthesis of branched architectures by polymerization of *n*BA through ARGET ATRP in miniemulsion controlled by reducing sugars present in honey

Figure S7. The influence of DP_{target} on polymerization of *n*BA from Trox-Br₁₀ by ARGET ATRP in miniemulsion controlled by reducing sugars present in honey. (a) Semilogarithmic kinetic plots, (b) evolutions of M_n and M_w/M_n vs monomer conversion. The influence of the $[Cu^{II}Br_2]_0/[RS]_0$ ratio on polymerization of *n*BA from Trox-Br₁₀ by ARGET ATRP in miniemulsion controlled by reducing sugars from honey. (c) Semilogarithmic kinetic plots, (d) evolutions of M_n and M_w/M_n vs monomer conversion. Reaction conditions as in **Table 6**, entry 1-3.

Figure S8. GPC traces of Trox-(PnBA)₁₀ prepared by ARGET ATRP in miniemulsion controlled by reducing sugars present honey using various conditions as follows: (a) DP_{target} = 600, [Cu^{II}Br₂]₀/[RS]₀ = 1/379 (**Table 6**, entry 1), (b) DP_{target} = 120, [Cu^{II}Br₂]₀/[RS]₀ = 1/379 (**Table 6**, entry 2), and (c) DP_{target} = 120, [Cu^{II}Br₂]₀/[RS]₀ = 1/10 (**Table 6**, entry 3).

Figure S9. Chain extension of *n*BA from Trox-(P*n*BA-Br)₁₀ macroinitiator using honey-inspired miniemulsion ARGET ATRP controlled by reducing sugars. (a) Semilogarithmic kinetic plot, (b) evolution of M_n and M_w/M_n vs monomer conversion, (c) GPC traces of the kinetics samples, and (d) GPC traces of the macroinitiator and the final product of chain extension experiment. Reaction conditions are listed in **Table 6**, entry 4.

Figure S10. Polymerization of *n*BA from Rib-Br₂ by ARGET ATRP in miniemulsion controlled by reducing sugars present honey in the presence and absence of hexadecane. (a) Semilogarithmic kinetic plots, (b) evolutions of M_n and M_w/M_n vs monomer conversion. The influence of targeted degree of polymerization on polymerization of *n*BA from Rib-Br₂ by ARGET ATRP in miniemulsion controlled by reducing sugars present honey. (c) Semilogarithmic kinetic plots, (d) evolutions of M_n

and M_w/M_n vs monomer conversion. The influence of the $[\text{Cu}^{\text{II}}\text{Br}_2]_0/[\text{RS}]_0$ ratio on polymerization of $n\text{BA}$ from Trox-Br₁₀ by ARGET ATRP in miniemulsion controlled by reducing sugars from honey. (e) Semilogarithmic kinetic plots, (f) evolutions of M_n and M_w/M_n vs monomer conversion. Reaction conditions as in **Table 7**.

Figure S11. GPC traces of Rib-(PnBA)₂ prepared by ARGET ATRP in miniemulsion controlled by reducing sugars present honey using various conditions as follows: (a) $\text{DP}_{\text{target}} = 600$, $[\text{Cu}^{\text{II}}\text{Br}_2]_0/[\text{RS}]_0 = 1/379$ (**Table 7**, entry 1), (b) $\text{DP}_{\text{target}} = 600$, $[\text{Cu}^{\text{II}}\text{Br}_2]_0/[\text{RS}]_0 = 1/379$, without HD (**Table 7**, entry 2), (c) $\text{DP}_{\text{target}} = 120$, $[\text{Cu}^{\text{II}}\text{Br}_2]_0/[\text{RS}]_0 = 1/10$ (**Table 7**, entry 3), and (d) $\text{DP}_{\text{target}} = 120$, $[\text{Cu}^{\text{II}}\text{Br}_2]_0/[\text{RS}]_0 = 1/10$ (**Table 7**, entry 4).

S8. Dynamic light scattering (DLS) analysis of miniemulsion droplets

Figure S12. DLS correlograms and intensity-averaged distribution of diameters of PnBA homopolymers prepared by ARGET ATRP in miniemulsion controlled by reducing sugars present honey using various conditions as follows: (a) $DP_{\text{target}} = 1200$, $[\text{Cu}^{\text{II}}\text{Br}_2]_0/[\text{RS}]_0 = 1/379$ (Table 5,

entry 1), (b) $DP_{\text{target}} = 120$, $[Cu^{II}Br_2]_0/[RS]_0 = 1/379$ (Table 5, entry 2), (c) $DP_{\text{target}} = 120$, $[Cu^{II}Br_2]_0/[RS]_0 = 1/10$ (Table 5, entry 3), (d) $DP_{\text{target}} = 120$, $[Cu^{II}Br_2]_0/[RS]_0 = 1/2$ (Table 5, entry 4), and (e) chain extension experiment, $DP_{\text{target}} = 1200$, $[Cu^{II}Br_2]_0/[RS]_0 = 1/10$ (Table 5, entry 5).

Figure S13. DLS correlograms and intensity-averaged distribution of diameters of Trox-(PnBA)₁₀ prepared by ARGET ATRP in miniemulsion controlled by reducing sugars present honey using various conditions as follows: (a) $DP_{\text{target}} = 600$, $[Cu^{II}Br_2]_0/[RS]_0 = 1/379$ (Table 6, entry 1), (b) $DP_{\text{target}} = 120$, $[Cu^{II}Br_2]_0/[RS]_0 = 1/379$ (Table 6, entry 2), (c) $DP_{\text{target}} = 120$, $[Cu^{II}Br_2]_0/[RS]_0 = 1/10$ (Table 6, entry 3), and (d) chain extension experiment, $DP_{\text{target}} = 1200$, $[Cu^{II}Br_2]_0/[RS]_0 = 1/379$ (Table 6, entry 4).

Figure S14. DLS correlograms and intensity-averaged distribution of diameters of Rib-(*PnBA*)₂ prepared by ARGET ATRP in miniemulsion controlled by reducing sugars present honey using various conditions as follows: (a) $DP_{\text{target}} = 600$, $[Cu^{II}Br_2]_0/[RS]_0 = 1/379$ (**Table 7**, entry 1), (b) $DP_{\text{target}} = 600$, $[Cu^{II}Br_2]_0/[RS]_0 = 1/379$, without HD (**Table 7**, entry 2), (c) $DP_{\text{target}} = 120$, $[Cu^{II}Br_2]_0/[RS]_0 = 1/10$ (**Table 7**, entry 3), and (d) $DP_{\text{target}} = 120$, $[Cu^{II}Br_2]_0/[RS]_0 = 1/10$ (**Table 7**, entry 4).

S9. Spectroscopic characterization of prepared polymers

The chemical shifts identified in the ^1H NMR spectrum in **Figure S15** (**Table 1**, entry 9) clearly evidenced PDMAEMA structure as follows: (500 MHz, CDCl_3) δ (ppm) = 0.61–1.20 (3H, CH_3 -, α), 1.66–2.08 (2H, $-\text{CH}_2$ -, β), 2.15–2.40 (6H, $\text{N}(\text{CH}_3)_2$, c), 2.46–2.76 (2H, $-\text{CH}_2$ -, b) and 3.64–4.42 (2H, $-\text{CH}_2$ -, a) [8].

Figure S15. ^1H NMR spectrum of PDMAEMA (after purification) in CDCl_3 (**Table 1**, entry 9).

The chemical shifts identified in the ^1H NMR spectrum in **Figure S16** (**Table 4**, entry 1) clearly evidenced PGMA structure as follows: (500 MHz, CDCl_3) δ (ppm) = 0.72–1.41 (3H, CH_3 -, α), 1.75–2.14 (2H, $-\text{CH}_2$ -, β), 2.51–3.00 (2H, $-\text{CH}_2$ -, c), 3.13–3.37 (1H, $-\text{CH}$ -, b), and 3.66–3.95 and 4.21–4.54 (2H, $-\text{CH}_2$ -, a) [9].

Figure S16. ^1H NMR spectrum of PGMA (after purification) in CDCl_3 (Table 4, entry 1).

The structure of the *Pn*BA linear polymers and branched macromolecules with *Pn*BA side chains were confirmed by ^1H NMR analysis (Figure S17-S19, respectively). Figure S17 showed a ^1H NMR spectrum for *Pn*BA linear polymers, while Figures S17 and S19 present the ^1H NMR spectra for branched polymers with *Pn*BA side chains and troxerutin or riboflavin core, respectively. The chemical shifts from *Pn*BA were indicated as follows: (500 MHz, CDCl_3) δ (ppm) = 0.77–1.03 (3H, CH_3 -, d), 1.19–2.06 (6H, CH_2 -, β + b + c), 2.14–2.52 (1H, $-\text{CH}-$, α), 3.69–4.36 (2H, CH_2 -, a) for linear polymers, 0.77–1.04 (3H, CH_3 -, d), 1.18–2.03 (6H, CH_2 -, β + b + c), 2.11–2.50 (1H, $-\text{CH}-$, α), 3.76–4.30 (2H, CH_2 -, a) for Trox-(*Pn*BA-Br)₁₀, and 0.75–1.02 (3H, CH_3 -, d), 1.14–2.04 (6H, CH_2 -, β + b + c), 2.19–2.45 (1H, $-\text{CH}-$, α), 3.83–4.26 (2H, CH_2 -, a) for Rib-(*Pn*BA-Br)₂ [7, 10].

Figure S17. ¹H NMR spectrum of PnBA (after purification) in CDCl₃ (Table 5, entry 3).

Figure S18. ¹H NMR spectrum of Trox-(PnBA-Br)₁₀ (after purification) in CDCl₃ (Table 6, entry 2).

Figure S19. ^1H NMR spectrum of Rib-(PnBA-Br)₂ (after purification) in CDCl_3 (Table 7, entry 1).

References

- [1] M.A. White, J.A. Johnson, J.T. Koberstein, N.J. Turro, *Journal of the American Chemical Society* 128 (35) (2006) 11356-11357. [10.1021/ja064041s](https://doi.org/10.1021/ja064041s).
- [2] I. Zaborniak, P. Chmielarz, *Polymers for Advanced Technologies* 31 (11) (2020) 2806-2815. <https://doi.org/10.1002/pat.5007>.
- [3] I. Zaborniak, K. Surmacz, M. Flejszar, P. Chmielarz, *Journal of Applied Polymer Science* 137 (42) (2020) 49275. <https://doi.org/10.1002/app.49275>.
- [4] J. Xia, K. Matyjaszewski, *Macromolecules* 32 (8) (1999) 2434-2437. <https://doi.org/10.1021/ma981694n>.
- [5] P. Chmielarz, *Polymer* 102 (2016) 192-198. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.polymer.2016.09.007>.
- [6] N.N. Deshavath, G. Mukherjee, V.V. Goud, V.D. Veeranki, C.V. Sastri, *International Journal of Biological Macromolecules* 156 (2020) 180-185. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijbiomac.2020.04.045>.
- [7] V.A. Williams, T.G. Ribelli, P. Chmielarz, S. Park, K. Matyjaszewski, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* 137 (4) (2015) 1428-1431. <https://doi.org/10.1021/ja512519j>.
- [8] I. Zaborniak, A. Macior, P. Chmielarz, M. Caceres Najarro, J. Iruthayaraj, *Polymer* 219 (2021) 123537. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.polymer.2021.123537>.
- [9] A. Hayek, Y. Xu, T. Okada, S. Barlow, X. Zhu, J.H. Moon, S.R. Marder, S. Yang, *J. Mater. Chem.* 18 (28) (2008) 3316-3318. [10.1039/B809656B](https://doi.org/10.1039/B809656B).
- [10] O. Eckardt, B. Wenn, P. Biehl, T. Junkers, F.H. Schacher, *React. Chem. Eng.* 2 (4) (2017) 479-486. <https://doi.org/10.1039/c7re00013h>.